

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B043
 Date: 27 Aug 2004
 Take Off: 07:57:20
 Landing: 12:55:37
 Flight Time: 4h58m17

Trials Instructions: ADRIEX - Operating Area:

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
4	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
5	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
6	CVI	Paul James	FAAM
7	WAS	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
10	Filters	Paola Formenti	CNRS/University of Paris 12
11	PAN	Ken Dewey	FAAM
12	AMS	Jonny Crosier	UMIST
13	AMS	Hugh Coe	UMIST
14	Mission Scientist 2	Ellie Highwood	Reading University
15	Mission Scientist 3	Jolene Cook	Reading University
16	Mission Scientist 4	Simon Osborne	Met Office
17	Mission Scientist 5	Gunnar Myhre	University of Oslo
18	Drosondes	Steve Devereau	FAAM
19	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight

Flight Track:

B043 Track 27-AUG-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b043
 Date: 27/08/04
 Project: ADRIEX
 Location: N Adriatic & Po Valley

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
075720		T/O	2.4 kft	230	From Treviso
080118	080921	Profile 1	5.3 - 13.6 kft	137	
080530		Video	9.4 kft	123	Start recording
081214	081349	Profile 1	13.7 - 15.0 kft	313	1000fpm
081628		Sonde	15.0 kft	317	Launch Sonde 001
081947	082607	Profile 2	15.0 - 9.0 kft	121	1000fpm , Interrupt
082802	083341	Profile 2	9.0 - 3.0 kft	303	
083500	084807	Run 1.1	3.0 kft	210	A to B
084920	090514	Run 1.2	3.0 kft	330	B to C
090626	091925	Run 1.3	3.0 kft	217	C to D
092035	093415	Run 1.4	3.0 kft	337	D to E
093444		Neph	3.0 kft	018	Cal
093835	095022	Profile 3	3.0 - 15.0 kft	160	1000fpm, E to D
095549	100833	Profile 4	15.0 - 3.0 kft	029	1000fpm, D to C
101332	103038	Run 2.1	3.0 kft	150	C to B
103204	104537	Run 2.2	3.0 kft	014	B to A
104652	105022	Profile 5	3.0 - 1.4 kft	124	500fpm
105230	105405	Profile 5	1.4 - 0.36 kft	306	
105655	105853	Orbit 1	0.36 - 0.34 kft	249	LH, 35deg, start 240
105853	110047	Orbit 2	0.34 kft	244	
110047	110238	Orbit 3	0.34 kft	230	
110239	110429	Orbit 4	0.34 - 0.35 kft	240	
110746		Videos	0.36 kft	131	Change tapes
111539	111737	Orbit 5	0.37 - 0.35 kft	247	LH, 35deg, start 240
111738	111930	Orbit 6	0.35 - 0.32 kft	253	
111930	112122	Orbit 7	0.32 - 0.34 kft	249	
112123	112319	Orbit 8	0.34 - 0.38 kft	251	SWS int time 75ms
112319	112523	Orbit 9	0.38 - 0.36 kft	248	SWS int time 75ms
112524	112729	Orbit 10	0.36 kft	247	
113247	113542	Run 3	0.07 - 0.12 kft	190	Into Sun
113613	113713	Run 3	0.07 - 0.13 kft	147	
114329	115032	Run 4	0.05 kft	194	Into Sun
115225	115855	Run 5	0.44 - 0.48 kft	020	Down Sun
120239	121139	Run 6	0.90 - 0.92 kft	201	Into Sun
121332	122108	Run 7	2.9 - 3.0 kft	030	Down Sun
122343	122953	Run 8	5.0 kft	214	Into Sun
123329	123821	Run 9	10.0 kft	033	Down Sun
125537		Land	0.03 kft	340	At Treviso
131100		UBBRs	0.00 kft	359	Covers ON
133403		EVM 1	0.00 kft	359	Stop Recording

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B043 Track 27-AUG-04

FAAM Sortie Brief

Flight Number: B043

Date 27th August 2004

Purpose: ADRIEX flight to investigate pollution in the Po Valley, Italy.

Weather: Predominantly cloud-free. Heavy pollution preferred.

Flight Pattern:

- 1) Take off Treviso 08:00Z.
- 2) Interrupted profile ascent at 1000ft/minute to FL150 towards point A (Ocean Tower at 45°18'51"N,12°30'29"E) (25mins).
- 3) Release Dropsonde #1 from FL150 over point A
- 4) Interrupted profile descent at 1000ft/minute over point A to 3000ft (40mins).
- 5) SLR at 3000ft from A to point B (44°30'N,12°00'E) (55mins).
- 6) SLR at 3000ft from B to point C at Soave (45°25'N,11°15'E) (75mins).
- 7) SLR at 3000ft from C to point D at Reggio Nell Emilia (44°42'N,10°32'E) (90mins).
- 8) SLR at 3000ft from from D to point E at (45°30'N,10°00'E) (105mins).
- 9) Profile ascent to FL150 from point E to point D (120mins).
- 10) Profile descent from FL150 to 3000ft from point D to point C (135mins) .
- 11) SLR at 3000ft from point C to point B (155mins).
- 12) SLR at 3000ft from point B to point A (170mins).
- 13) Profile descent to 400ft at 500ft/minute (175mins).
- 14) Set of banked orbits over point A at the solar zenith angle (~35°) (190mins).
- 15) Holding pattern for 10minutes (200mins).
- 16) Set of banked orbits over point A at the solar zenith angle (~35°) (210mins).
- 17) Stacked profile ascent with 5 SLRs of 10-minute duration orientated into- and down- sun at different levels to be determined by the aircraft scientist over point A (270mins).
- 18) Release Dropsonde #2 from highest level reached in (17) over point A
- 19) Recover to Treviso (290mins).

Point A (Ocean Tower)	45°18'51"N,12°30'29"E
Point B	44°30'N,12°00'E
Point C (Soave)	45°25'N,11°15'E
Point D (Reggio Nell Emilia)	44°42'N,10°32'E
Point E	45°30'N,10°00'E

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B043

Date: 27th August 2004

Sortie Objectives: ADRIEX flight #1. To investigate the pollution up the Po Valley using in-situ measurements and to make radiometric and in-situ measurements in conjunction with the ocean tower.

Operating area: Po Valley and ocean areas over the northern Adriatic Ocean. 5 points were defined:-

A:-	Ocean Tower	45°18'51''N, 12°30'29'E
B:-		44°30'N, 12°00'E
C:-	Soave	45°25'N, 11°15'E
D:-	Reggio Nell Emilia	44°42'N, 10°32'E
E:-		44°30'N, 10°00'E

Weather: Organised thundery rain on the morning of the previous day associated with a frontal system had washed out a significant amount of the pollution. During the flight high level Ci progressively intruded from the west. Very light pollution levels – will make a very good clean-comparison case.

Flight Patterns:

Take off from Treviso at ~07:58. Profile ascent to FL150 over the ocean tower and a dropsonde was launched from over the tower. A profile descent was then performed to 3000ft back to point A. Permission to drop sondes was suspended. A zig-zag pattern at 3000ft was then performed up the Po Valley from point A->B->C->D->E. The aircraft was in the boundary layer for the duration of these legs and various local pollution sources were detected by AMS, and nephelometer. A reciprocal heading was then flown down the Po Valley from E->D->C->B->A with a profile ascent/descent 3000ft-FL150-3000ft from E->D and from D->C. At the ocean tower at point A, a profile descent was performed to 400ft where two sets of ~35° banked orbits were performed. A set of SLRs were then performed orientated into- and down-sun at 100ft, 500ft, 1000ft, 3000ft, 5000ft, and FL100 to the immediate south of the ocean tower located at point A.

Summary:

A successful flight in close to completely clean conditions. Aerosol optical depths were low over the Adriatic throughout the day (AERONET) suggests 440nm AODs of 0.104 (ISDGM, central Venice), 0.064 (Ocean tower), 0.078 (Nicelli Airport). but local fresh pollution was measured up the Po Valley. A successful flight for the SWS instrument which performed well – it was possible to locate the solar disc in both fore and aft positions for solar zenith angles. Neutral density filters 2+1 stopped module 1 from saturating when looking at the sun.

Problems:

Nephelometer failed after a calibration run and did not work after that.

Nephelometer pressure still shows signs of irregularities.

Wing PCASP still showing noise and first two channels missing.

CVI PCASP showing no figure on Ch1?

ISDGM-CUR LI = $\frac{27}{0.104}$ $\frac{28}{0.152}$
 Tower Night LI = 0.064 $\frac{0.119}{0.127}$
 LI = $\frac{0.078}{0.127}$

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Ascent towards A
 FL150 sonde
 P ↓ 3000ft
 ↓ V/S

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Date 27/August 2004

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					RyanAir bird impact on aircraft T/O ~ 5 mins before T/O
~07:58			300M		T/O Treviso.
					Heavy pollution at low levels in Po valley - looks to be in lowest 1000ft or so.
					Some very tenuous Ci. Very 0/8 Cu, 1/8 Ci.
08:01:18	St P1	5000ft	120M		Start Profile 1 at 1000ft/ min.
					Overshooting point A.
08:09:21	Int P1	FL136			Hazy below, but not much off coast, mostly up the Po Valley.
08:12:14	Restart P1	FL136↑			
08:13:49	End P1	FL150			End P1, prep dropsonde.
08:16:30	D#1				Dropsonde #1. Good!
08:19:47	P2	FL150 ↓			1000ft/min.
08:26:07	Int P2	FL90 →			Heading 255T shows big pollution layers.
08:28:02	Cont P2	FL90 ↓	306T		
08:33:41	End P2	FL90 3000ft			
08:35:00	St R1.1	→ 3000ft	207T		A → B at 3000ft.
					Some Cu at 3000ft to RHS of aircraft.
08:48:07	End R1.1	→ 3000ft			B → C at 3000ft.
08:49:20	St R1.2	→ 3000ft			Windspeed 1.7ms ⁻¹ Direction 20°-30°

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	(1.2cont)	3000ft	329T	Lat 44.7 Lon 11.8	T 17.4, TD 3.2
08:55:					Over to Po.
09:05:14	End R1.2	3000ft	216T		
09:06:26	3 rd R1.3				C → D
					Working up Po Valley
9:15:00					Layers of pollution to RHS at this level. Distinct clear slot. was ← yesterday? was → today
9:16:00					Chemistry tracers picking up → CO & O ₂ .
09:19:25	End R1.3				
09:20:35	5 th R1.4				D. → E
					Good correlation between O ₃ + CO. PCASP has some problems in ch 3. (ch 1 + ch 2 are OFF). AMS reports lots of <u>NO₃</u> + organics, little to no SO ₄ .
					BBR signals + zeros look good.
09:30.					Pollution + PCASP + gas phase dropping off.
09:34:15	End 1.4				Lots of vineyards etc here.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:38:35	P3	3000ft ↑	160T		E → D. Profile ascent at 1000ft/min
09:50:22	End P3	FL150.			Procedure turn for CO calibration.
09:55:49	Start P4	FL150 ↓	28T		1000ft/min descent. Splashdown 45.17.55N of sands 12.13.25E. Sands-drops suspended
					2 miles to S. of Ocean tower. (bumps)
10:07:00		3700ft			Top of BL n885mb 3,700ft.
10:08:33	End P4	3000ft			
10:13:32	Start R2.1	3000ft →	148T		C → B. Quite bumpy → surface heating getting going. Nephelometer problems seem to be <u>bad</u> Crashes from trace restarts every 3 minutes or so.
10:30:38	End R2.1	3000ft →			
10:32:04	R2.2	3000ft →			St Run B → A Bumpy scattered (< 1/8 km. Bases above us, estimated 4000ft. Only a few hundred ft.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

100 ft
500
1000
3000
5000
5000 ft.

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:45:47	End R2.2	3000ft			Profile §
10:46:52	P5	300ft ↓			
10:50:22	Int P5	1500ft ↗			Reciprocal turn
10:52:30	Restart P5	1500ft ↓	307.		
10:54:05	End P5	400ft ↗			
10:56:55	O1	400ft ↻	St 240	Pt A	35° Left wing down
10:58:53	End O1 / St O2	"	"		Some patchy Ci
11:02:57	End O2 / St O3	"	"		Very little cloud ^{above} around .
11:02:39	End O3 / St O4	"	"		Very little Ci, not
11:04:29	End O4	↗			much aerosol above.
					Holding pattern while filters put in
					changed → can use the data ~ 700 - 400ft.
11:15:39	St O5	400ft ↻	St 240	Pt A	35° LWD
11:17:38	End O5 / St O6	"	"		T22C, TD 15.8C
11:19:30	End O6 / St O7	"	"		Almost no Ci above
11:21:23	End O7 / St O8	"	"		Pretty damn low
11:23:19	End O8 / St O9	"	"		AGDS
11:25:24	End O9 / St O10	"	"		Sza 35.6°
11:25:24	End O10	"	"		Sazim 184.4°
					pitchub°
					<u>Excellent orbits.</u>
					Reposition fr.
11:32:47	St R3	100ft	188		Clear above
11:35:42	End R3				Reposition

8:55
-10:45
↓
~ 2 hrs

11:36:13.

4:10

FL 300

Aircraft Scientist's Log

100 ✓
500 ✓
1000 ✓
3000 ✓
5000 ✓
10000 ✓

Flight No **B**.....043.....

Date27 August.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Reposition as too close to land.
11:43:29	St R4	100ft	196		Into sun run. Lost Rad Contact Free from most Ci. Ci to W not affecting Cu to E. BBRs here though * 11:49 → change in ocean colour
11:50:32	End R4	100ft			Good run. Free from Ci.
11:52:25	St R5	500ft			Down-sun A few contrails, very minor
11:58:55	End R5	500ft			Looks very good.
12:02:38	Start R6	1000ft			Into-sun Ci to W → not interfering with solar disk at all.
12:04:39	End R6	1000ft			
12:13:32	St R7	3000ft			Down-sun
12:21:08	End R7	3000ft			Ci increasing for BBRs.
12:23:43	R8	5000ft			Into-sun A few
12:29:53	End R8	5000ft			contrails at end of run.
12:33:29	St R9	FL100			Down-sun
12:38:21	End R9				Drifted off off sun at the end. Cu over land by 12:45.
					Probably R4-R7 will be free from significant Ci. Not very much pollution though

BL Top at FL650 over land/ocean interface
land

~12:58

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Date: 27/8/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:	Ch1-Ch3	Noise	Too Noisy								Start Profile 1
08:03:07	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			2						FL070
08:04:20	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			2						FL080
08:05:20	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									FL090
08:06:12	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									FL100 PCASP Heaters ON
08:07:15	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			2						FL110
08:	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									FL120
08:	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									FL140
08:14:10	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									End of Profile 1 @ FL150
08:19:47	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									Start Profile 2 from FL150
08:21:30	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			1						FL140
08:22:14	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			1						FL130
08:25:04	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			1						FL100
08:26:06	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			1						FL090
08:29:20	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			1						FL080
08:33:41	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									End of Profile 2 @ 3000'
08:35:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									Start Run 1.1 @ 3000'
08:36:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			10						
08:38:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			8						
08:40:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			5						
08:42:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			8						
08:44:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			8						
08:46:00	Ch1-Ch3	Noise			5						
08:48:07	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									End of Run 1.1
08:49:13	Ch1-Ch3	Noise									Start Run 1.2 @ 3000'
08:50:00	100				5						
08:52:00	80				5						
08:54:00	80				5						
08:56:00	50				5						
08:58:00	50				5						
09:00:00	50				5						PCASP heaters ON
09:02:00	150				10						

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B043

Date: 27/8/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:04:00	150			10							
09:05:09											End of Run
09:06:26											Start Run 1.3 @ 3000'
09:07:00	100			10							
09:09:00	100			8							
09:11:00	150			8							
09:13:00	150			8							
09:15:00	200			10							
09:17:00	100			5							
09:19:25											End of Run 1.3
09:20:35											Start Run 1.4 @ 3000'
09:21:00	500			10							
09:23:00	500			12							
09:25:00	300			12							
09:27:00	300			12							
09:29:00	300			10							
09:31:00	30			2							
09:33:00	30			2							
09:34:15											End of Run 1.4
09:38:35											Start P3 from FL030
09:39:47	20			1							FL040
09:40:43	10			1							FL050
09:41:48	10										FL060
09:44:50	5										FL090
09:45:55	5										FL100
09:46:50	5										FL110
09:49:30	3										FL120
09:50:20											End of P3 @ FL150
09:55:49											Start Profile 4 from FL150
09:57:09	1										FL140
09:58:25	20			1							FL130
09:59:30	20			1							FL120 PCASP Heaters OFF

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:00:27	30			1							FL110
10:01:30	25			1							FL100
10:03:25	100			1							FL080
10:04:30	80			1							FL070
10:05:28	80			1							FL060
10:06:30	100			2							FL050
10:07:30	100			3							FL040
10:08:35	100			2							End of Profile 4 @ FL030
10:13:32											Start Run 2.1 @ FL030
10:14:00	50			1							
10:16:00	30			1							
10:18:00	50			2							
10:20:00	200			5							
10:22:00	150			10							
10:24:00	100			5							
10:26:00	150			10							
10:28:00	150			10							
10:30:00	50			5							
10:30:38											End of Run 2.1
10:32:04											Start Run 2.1 @ FL030
10:33:00	100			5							
10:35:00	150			10							
10:37:00	100			8							
10:39:00	50			8							
10:41:00	30			5							
10:43:00	25			3							
10:45:00	20			2							
10:45:37											End of Run 2.1
10:46:52											Start Profile 5 From FL030
10:48:32	20			5							FL020
10:52:50	25			2							FL010
10:54:05	25			2							End of Profile 5 @ 400'

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Operator:MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:56:55											Start Orbits @ 400'
11:04:29											End of 4 th Orbit
11:15:40											Start Orbits @ 400'
11:27:39											End of 8 th Orbit
11:32:47											Start Run 3 @ 100'
11:33:00	40			2							
11:35:02											End of Run 3
11:36:13											Cont Run
11:37:00	30			5							
11:37:05											End of Run 3
11:43:29											Start Run 4 @ 100'
11:44:00	30			3							
11:46:00	20			2							
11:48:00	20			2							
11:50:20											End of Run 4
11:52:25											Start Run 5 @ 500'
11:53:00	40			5							
11:55:00	40			5							
11:57:00	35			3							
11:58:55											End of Run 5
12:02:39											Start Run 6 @ 1000'
12:03:00	15			2							
12:05:00	15			2							
12:07:00	15			2							
12:09:00	15			2							
12:11:39											End of Run 6
12:13:32											Start Run 7 @ 3000'
12:14:00	30			2							
12:16:00	25			2							
12:18:00	20			2							
12:20:00	20			2							
12:21:08											End of Run 7

SWS/SHIMS PRE-FLIGHT LOG		Date	27/8/04	Flight	B043
Operator(s)	A. Wilson		Campaign	ADRIEX	
Departure	27 075722 Z		Arrival	27 125545	

Physical system setup

Module Number Serial	Connection(e.g.SWS nir, SHIMS upper)
0	SWS NIR
27581	SWS VIS

System functionality check **After system stabilizes**

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0 Sec	at time	073800Z
Freezer temp	-8°C			

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 043a	Date	27/8/04	Operator(s)	A. Wilson	log page	1	of	2
Time Z	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks Note remark *2 - flight glitch.			
				Vis	NIR				

27074801						take off Data start			
074801						DARK current			
074801						Video start record			
075000			90		Auto	Data start			
075722			90			take off			
080118	P1	053	0°						
080650						Accidental PC Reset			
080921		136				interrupt P1			
081214						recommencing P1			
081310						Data restart - Dark current			
081329	P1					End P1 - Dark current			
081930			0°			Program restart - Dark current.			
						Flight renamed B043a			
						Return			
081947	P2					start			
082100			0°			Data start			
082607	P2	090				interrupt			
082802	P2	090	0°			recommence P2			
083344		030	0°			end			
083500	R1.1	030	0°			start			
084030						NIR int increased to allow 1000ms			
084807	R1.1	030°	0°			end			
084920	R1.2	±	180°			start			
090514	R1.2		0°			end. NIR int increased to allow 1500ms.			
090626	R1.3	030	180			start + 2000ms.			
090840						Accidental Dark current - without shutter.			
091925	R1.3	030	0°/180°			END Run			
092035	R1.4	030	180°			START Run			
093415	R1.4	030	180°			END Run			
093447						Dark current measure (took 2min 50)			
093835	P2	030-150	0°			to PL150 @ Point D			
095022	P3	150	0°			END P2 @ D			
095549	P4	150-030	180°			Start P4 @ D			
100833	P4	030	180°			END P4 @ C			
100915		030	0°			change to up view.			
101332	R2.1	030	0°			start @ Point C			
103015						current solar zenith angle 36°			
103038	R2.1					END @ Point B			
103204	R2.2	030	180°			START @ Point B			
104345					200ms 200ms	over sea sample period set to 4Secs			
104537	R2.2					END @ Point A			
104652	P5	030-004				start P5 FL030-400ft			

* 1

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CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B043	DATE: 27/08/2004	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 1 of 1
LOCATION: Po Valley, N Italy		PROJECT: ADRIEX flight to investigate pollution in the Po Valley, Italy	

GAS CYLINDER PRESSURES	N2	Argon/CO2	CO
PRE FLIGHT	psi / bar	psi / bar	psi / bar
POST FLIGHT	psi / bar	psi / bar	psi / bar

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 (ppb)	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)		
24/08/04	?	?	91			-	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: last calibration data from previous flight for comparison with today.													
27/08/04	GROUND	-	92.27	65.86	6076.96	-	-	-	-	-	-		
07:30:47	Remarks: First cal of day. Air Sample pipe closed. Max cal reading was 600, should be 525 so another cal reqd.												
07:35:10	Ground	-	89.39	67.72	6053.71	228.164	-	-	-	-	-		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr	Press Cell:	Press Cal Gas	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C			
Remarks: Air Sample pipe closed. Max values now 512-510 so a little low but better than 600.													
07:55:57	Ground	Taxiing	92.81	67.83	6295.82	261.260	10	6.86	9.9	16.76	6.49		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr	Press Cell:	Press Cal Gas	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C			
Remarks: Air Sample pipe closed. Cal while taxiing post ground to air power changeover reboot of CO.													
08:37:11	3000'	R1.1	90.41	68.13	6159.98	106.050	48	-0.00	0.49	0.49	5.29		
	Flow Lamp:	34.01	Press Monocr	0.77	Press Cell:	7.16	Press Cal Gas	2.33	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	24.67	PMT °C
Remarks: Cal started before R1.1 began and completed approx 2 min into run.													
09:37:38	3000'	-	91.07	66.02	6012.02	103.977	52	-0.51	-0.28	-0.23	5.41		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr	Press Cell:	Press Cal Gas	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C			
Remarks: ?CO & Noxy cal during 3 min turn post R1.4. CO max 525-535 O3 dropped from 51/2 to 21/4 with slight lag during Noxy cal.													
09:53:49	FL150	-	90.43	65.43	5916.89	85.652	46	0.04	0.18	0.23	7.14		
	Flow Lamp:	33.98	Press Monocr	0.76	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.27	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	24.79	PMT °C
Remarks: Cal started 09:50:25													
10:11:56	FL030	-	91.45	65.49	5989.15	120.229	50	0.35	0.68	1.03	5.03		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr	Press Cell:	Press Cal Gas	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C			
Remarks: Cal during 'long turn' at end of profile descent and pre 3000' level run													
10:44:22	FL030	R2.2	91.60	65.21	5973.53	108.630	53	0.03	0.44	0.48	5.14		
	Flow Lamp:	34.01	Press Monocr	0.76	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.33	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	24.96	PMT °C
Remarks: Cal during last three mins of R2.2.													
11:10:23	FL004	-	91.00	64.76	5893.33	111.729	50	0.04	0.60	0.64	5.59		
	Flow Lamp:	33.94	Press Monocr	0.76	Press Cell:	7.16	Press Cal Gas	2.32	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.66	PMT °C
Remarks: Cal during holding pattern. After the cal the CO value dropped ~10ppb so another cal was carried out.													
11:15:48	FL004	-	90.87	64.96	5903.65	120	48	0.12	1.05	1.17	5.81		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr	Press Cell:	Press Cal Gas	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C			
Remarks: Cal finished ~ 10 seconds into orbit. CO conc. Now back to the expected value of 120.													
11:36:08	FL001	R3	89.68	65.53	5876.03	114.956	49	-0.16	0.66	0.55	-		
	Flow Lamp:	34.24	Press Monocr	0.76	Press Cell:	7.16	Press Cal Gas	2.32	Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks: Cal started as 100' run called though aircraft was still descending from 130' into the 100' run..													
11:55:38	FL005	R4	88.64	65.86	5837.73	110.592	50	-0.10	0.42	0.32	5.47		
	Flow Lamp:	33.76	Press Monocr	0.76	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.32	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.54	PMT °C
Remarks: Started cal a few minutes before start of R4.													
12:06:11	FL010	R6	88.17	65.97	5816.59	110.404	51	-0.01	0.49	0.48	5.64		
	Flow Lamp:	34.09	Press Monocr	0.76	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.32	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.61	PMT °C
Remarks:													
12:16:46	FL030	R7	87.71	66.48	5830.49	105.280	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks:													
12:27:11	FL050	R8	87.65	66.26	5808.02	107.753	55	-0.07	0.46	0.40	-		
Remarks:													
12:36:47	FL100	R9	87.62	65.89	5773.50	99.017	54	0.03	0.01	0.04	6.37		
Remarks:													
12:49:	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: Air sample pipes closed													

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

 Flight No. **B.043**.....

 Date **27.8.04**.....

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU			<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		✓	FFSSP		✓
Satcom C		✓	PCASP		✓
Satcom H		✓	2D-P		X
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C		X
De-Iced Temp			Cloudscope		
Non De-Iced		✓	SID 1		✓
Heimann		✓	SID 2		X
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI		X
G. Eastern		✓	HVPS		X
J. Williams		✓	<u>Racks:</u>		
Nevzorov	X		INC		X
TWC	X		CCN/CNC		✓
FWVS		✓	CVI		✓
<u>Radiometers</u>					
Upper Clear			<u>Aerosol</u>		
“ Red		✓	PSAP		
“ Silicon		X	Nephelometer		✓
“ JO1D		X	AMS		✓
Lower Clear					
“ Red		✓			
“ Silicon		X			
“ JO1D		X			
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	X				
MARSS	X				
DEIMOS	X				
ARIES	X				
SWS / SHM		✓			
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone		✓			
ECGC		X			
NOX		✓			
CO		✓	<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC		X			
PAN		✓			
PERCA		X			
WAS		✓			

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B043.

Instruments

1. Upper BBRs - tried moving clr + red onto card 2 + swap addresses of Card 1 (was 10h) + Card 2 (was 14h). No good, when done swapped, clr = 88W, red = -2.
2. HORACE plotting time 25 ahead of AMTG.
3. Dropsande: message saved as .txt, Horace looking for .xxx
4. Cloud Phys: PCASP data noisy, faulty psu?
FFSSP noisy too.
5. Dropsande - dispute between Padova and Rome.
6. Nephelometer - all scattering signals to -0.9 m^{-1} . Tried sw off/on no change. sw off for 15 mins, worked for a while then -0.9 . Tried cal. then okay. (at 1150)
7. CVI - computer screen damaged
8. RFC - picture over-exposed most of flight
9. AFC - smudge on picture twds top right corner.

Aircraft

Intercom: Fm headset no transmit at engine start - is it switched off?
AS headset - very quiet on tx - swap for spare Core Chem
SRD " " " " "
Filters " - VERY faint

?

B043 27-Aug-04 07:44:15 000 (05:38:37) 45.65 12.2

Event mark

<input type="radio"/> 81.UPOS	7965	24349	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="radio"/> 82.UPIS	1799	26375	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="radio"/> 84.UPOZ	799	8991	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="radio"/> 85.UPIZ	1345	9537	<input type="radio"/>

N/A	N/A

81.UPP VIS CLR SIG
 82.UPP VIS RED SIG
 83.UPP I/R SIGNAL
 84.UPP VIS CLR ZERO
 85.UPP VIS RED ZERO

07392

B043 27-Aug-04 09:33:20 000 (05:38:37) 45.44 10.0

Event mark

81.UPOS	1331	34099	
82.UPIS	4016	36784	
84.UPOZ	9007	9007	
85.UPIZ	9565	9565	

N/A	N/A

81.UPP VIS CLR SIG
82.UPP VIS RED SIG
83.UPP I/R SIGNAL
84.UPP VIS CLR ZERO
85.UPP VIS RED ZERO

B043 27-Aug-04 10:39:19 000 (05:38:37) 44.95 12.2

Event mark

○ 81.UPOS	3725	36493	○
○ 82.UPI5	6283	39051	○
○ 84.UPOZ	9000	9000	○
○ 85.UPIZ	9570	9570	○

N/A	N/A

81.UPP VIS CLR SIG
 82.UPP VIS RED SIG
 83.UPP I/R SIGNAL
 84.UPP VIS CLR ZERO
 85.UPP VIS RED ZERO

B043 27-Aug-04 13:01:03 000 (05:38:37) 45.65 12.2

Event mark

<input type="radio"/> 81.UPOS	14624	14624	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="radio"/> 82.UPI5	13546	13546	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="radio"/> 84.UPOZ	8942	8942	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="radio"/> 85.UPIZ	9613	9613	<input type="radio"/>

N/A	N/A

81.UPP VIS CLR SIG
82.UPP VIS RED SIG
83.UPP I/R SIGNAL
84.UPP VIS CLR ZERO
85.UPP VIS RED ZERO